

Work and Family Conflicts, Its Relationship with Employees' Well - Being: How Supervisor's Emotional Support moderates this relationship

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Abstract

This study tends to enlarge volume of quality work available on work family conflict. It also examines the link between work family conflict with employees' well-being and moderating role of supervisory emotional support. By studying the moderating effect of supervisory emotional support on work family conflict causes to increase the worth of current study as these relations are rarely studied by the researchers. In order to conduct the study data has been gathered from 150 employees of service providing industries located in Skardu, Pakistan like banks, schools, colleges, offices through convenience sampling. The participants were asked to complete a questionnaire which included sets of questions about each variable. The author used three steps hierarchical regression and correlation for the purpose of data analysis. Three step hierarchical regression analyses indicated that employees experiencing work family conflict reported to affect their well-being negatively. As predicted Supervisory emotional support acts as moderator. Contrary to expectation supervisory emotional support failed to show its direct impact on employees' well-being. This study will definitely provide assistance for managers and HR professionals along with all other types of managers to understand the importance of well-being of employees and give direction for

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management to focus on providing supervisory emotional support to them so that the organization will be able to have more satisfied employees.

Keywords: Work family conflict, Supervisor’s emotional support, and employees’ well-being,

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1 Introduction

In this competitive world every organization desires to achieve its pre-defined goals and objectives effectively for this purpose the organizations try to create and maintain the environment in which employees work more comfortably because employees are the resource of the organization. If they have the environment without any conflict specially work family conflict they can give best performance and hence causes to enhance the performance of the organization. (Ernst et al., 1998), found that work family-conflict is a two process: First one demonstrates the clashes emerging when work parts intervene with family parts that causes work to family conflict and the second one indicates issues emerging as a result of intervention of family related parts with work part which causes family to work conflict. Family work conflict is a mismatch between family responsibilities and work pressure. It can be seen when demands from one area causes to influence the performance of individual in other domain. For instance, when one gives additional time to work part, the family part will suffer (Greenhouse et al., 1985).

Continuous changes in workplace because of work family conflict causes researchers to get more insight of the relationship between work and family tug of war. Work and family issues affect the overall performance of the employees (Netemeyer et al., 1996). As it is said by (Allen et al., 2001), that work and family conflict work-family is an important reason that generates stress among employees. According to (Greenhaus et al., 1985), three issues bring work-family conflicts in individual's life which is time based conflict, behaviour based conflict and strain based conflicts. Time-based conflict is the conflict that emerges when the time committed to one part becomes tough for the individual to take an interest in the other part. For example, when an individual have to attend meeting with teacher of his child and it may collide with an important meeting at office. Strain based conflict can be there when strains created in one-part overflow other part. Thus symptoms like anxiety, fatigue, and irritability will be experienced by the individual while behaviour based conflict arises at the point when certain example of in-role behaviour becomes unfit to exist together with hope to perform effectively in other to conduct in another part.

Employees' well-being can be defined as one's general psychological health status or mental condition particularly relates with a worker's level of satisfaction, uneasiness, stress, and discouragement (Goldberg et al., 1972). The combination of job related stress and personal stress induce drastic harmful physical and emotional results by setting excessive demands on body and mind (Cooper et al., 1994).

Different researchers have already worked on studying the impact of work-family conflict on employees well-being and found negative relation between them (Lizano et al., 2014), but still there is capacity to investigate the relationship in various part of the world and on various specimens from various fields with the goal to measure the individual's responses, experiences and behaviours.

The present study is focusing on investigating the influence of work-family conflict on employees' wellbeing by choosing supervisory emotional support as a moderator. So, present study has done to inspect the impact of work-family conflict on employees' wellbeing. Lizano et al., 2014, directed to study the moderating influence of family supportive supervisory behaviour on the work-family conflict and employees' wellbeing relationship. There for in current study author is going to focus one of the dimensions of family supportive supervisory behaviour (FSSB) which is supervisory emotional support.

Supervisory emotional support means the care, trust, empathy, support and concern provided by the immediate supervisor in work place (Jayaratne et al., 1984). The family

supportive supervisor is the one who profoundly tries to know the worker's need to look for stability between family and work obligations (Thomas et al., 1995).

Modern work identified four dimension of FSSB and they are creative work family management, emotional support, role modelling support and instrumental support (Hammer et al., 2009). In this study only one dimension is going to be studied as moderating variable and that is supervisory emotional support.

Work-family conflict and well-being relationship is studied by different researchers in past decades (Lourel et al., 2009). Lizano et al., 2014, studied this relationship in California by taking supervisory support and organizational support as moderator. They have encouraged new researchers to build the volume of writing as small number of study has been carried out so far in studying work family conflict and worker's well-being. The researchers further suggested to make use of a variable showing specific family supportive supervisory behaviour in relation with wellbeing of employees and work-family conflict and so in this research one of the dimensions of family-supportive supervisory behaviour (FSSB) is taken i.e. supervisory emotional support.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Work-Family Conflict (WFC)

Work and family are two very important areas of life. Recently in few years, research increases enormously in investigating the relation between job pressure and family lives (Edwards et al., 2000).

WFC is described as the extent to which a person's interest in one part intervene with his/her capacity to meet the duties of another part (Brosschot et al., 2006). The clash between demands of family and work can be classified in two focal measurements: work-family conflict and family-work domain (Carlson et al., 2000). When family expectation and job demands clash together, it gives birth to work-life conflict (Netemeyer et al., 1996). Greenhaus et al., 1985, portrayed WFC as a sort of conflict in which pressure from pressure from both family and work zones usually opposing each other, for instance job and task in the work or family part becomes hard to be performed if pressure from one domain interfere second domain. Researchers have been progressively showed interest in studying WFC in the course of recent decades.

WFC is a vital issue which directly influences the prosperity, as family and work are the most important parts of one's life. Greenhaus et al., 2006, said work-family conflict negatively influences the flourishing of individuals and organization.

The literature in work family conflict has recognized it as a major reason behind psychological strain among professional in different fields (Ernst Kossek et al., 2012). Researchers reported that work to family and family to work conflict are adversely connected to work fulfilment, family fulfilment, and well-being (Kinnunen et al., 2004). There are several theories proposed by researchers to explain WFC. In 1964 the role theory was presented by Wolfe, Kahn, Rosenthal, Quinn and Snoek according to them it depends on human strength and impacts of different roles performed by individual on wellbeing and prosperity.

The probability of a person encountering role conflict increases with an increase in the quantity of his or her role in his life (Marks et al., 1977). It define that individual has limited time, energy and attention but has to perform different roles in his life, he has to perform different task and activities in workplace and at home as well and this limited time and energy may be the root cause of generating work family conflict (Goode et al., 1960). Theories

and research comes about supporting this point of view demonstrate that the blend of family and work frequently makes a greater number of pressure than one can deal with - prompting part over-burden. Thus, there is a high danger of part clashes: work in the home frequently clashes with paid work outside the home. So in long term, the pressure can achieve stress and mental disease (Nordenmark et al., 2002). Grzywacz et al., 2000, refers to spill over theory, as indicated that any sentiments, mentalities, feelings and practices produced in single area can cause to effect or 'overflowed' into the other part. It is considered one of the highest rank theories in studying work and family interface (Grzywacz et al., 2002). The spill over impacts can be positive or negative. Positive spill over happens when the feeling of achievement and fulfilment in one area (e.g., work) are exchanged to another space (e.g., home). For example, an employee who has effectively fulfilled all undertakings at work may feel glad, calm and satisfy at home as well.

2.2 WFC and Employee's Wellbeing;

At point when organizations are not dealing with their workers and their problems, social and money related results follows (Noor et al., 2004). Its matter of fact that employees don't leave all their work related stress at work often such kind of issues causes to intervene in non-work lives as well (Song et al., 2008; Ilies et al., 2007). When employees faces any sort of conflict at office and will not be able to psychologically disconnect from that conflict even at home, it is likely to be expected that they keep imagining and thinking about conflict it ultimately causes to create stress and strain in employees (Brosschot et al., 2006).

Work family conflict is connected to negative results for individual, families, and organization. It is related with work disappointment, affects general well-being, goal to turnover, and psychological disorder (Netemeyer et al., 1996). Work family clashes with employee's well-being of workers and organizational success (Dobrevva et al., 2002). Conflict has direct effect on the prosperity of employees and the execution of performance will also be suffered (Lingard et al., 2006). Work-family conflict reduces satisfaction hence causes to bring down intensity of well-being (Frone et al., 1992). The researchers have verified that work-family conflict is linked to reduction in satisfaction level and causes to lower the levels of mental prosperity (Ernst Kossek et al., 2012).

WFC is one of the major cause which induces stress and ultimately affects the employees psychologically and physically (Noor, 2004). Work family conflict causes strain and physical side effects which causes the employees to divert their attention and further decrease their wellbeing (Winefield et al., 2014). Researchers found that such conflict causes to affects the person's emotion and physical condition, as a result causing loses for organizations because of absentees (Cooper et al., 1994).

When the work intervenes with individual's family life, he may experience problems to respond accordingly to family requests and vice versa. Hence causes to affect their performance and well-being (Frone et al., 1992). Researches from West have exposed the fact that both work-family and family-work conflict are related to wellbeing (Mesmer et al., 2009). Lu et al., 2006, discovered in his study that work family conflicts were adversely associated with satisfaction for Taiwanese workers.

On the basis of above literature, we can hypothesize that:

H1: *Work-family conflict is in negative relation with employees' well-being.*

2.3 Supervisory Emotional Support and Employees' well-being:

Social support is defined as the form of support which can be provided in form care, emotional support and guidelines related to the job etc. (Md-Sidin et al, 2010). Social support has the important impact and act as a moderator in studying the relation among job satisfaction and emotional exhaustion (Um et al., 1998). Getting emotional support is linked to employees well-being (Nahum et al., 2011). Employees who receive support from their supervisors causes to reduce burnout effect (Muhammad et al., 2005). Social support causes to reduce stress among employees and tends to increase well-being (Gurung et al., 1997). Emotional support at work environment tends to increase the better relation between employees and employers and hence can improve well-being. (Harris et al., 2007). In working environment social support can be viewed as an important apparatus for avoiding work related stress (Cohen et al., 1985). All types of support from supervisor including emotional support causes to reduce the stress and anxiety of the employees in workplace. (Cohen et al., 1985). Lack of social support causes to have hypertension depression, absence because of sickness, cardiovascular diseases and several disorders (Bowen et al., 1988). Conduct of supervisors can be fundamentally related with the well-being of their workers (Gilbreath et al., 2004). Dunseath et al., 1995, support provided by immediate boss to the employees is one of the most significant form of support at workplace which causes to reduces job stress. In study conducted by Hsu et al., 2010, they found that, supervisory help can cause to successfully moderate the work-family conflict.

From available literature we can hypothesize that:

H2: Supervisory emotional support increases employees' well-being.

2.4 Work-Family conflict and Employee Wellbeing, Moderating Role of Supervisory Emotional Support:

Managers' family-supportive behaviours i-e role modelling behaviours, creative work-family management, emotional support and instrumental support, can causes to decrease work-to-family conflict (Behson et al., 2005). Supervisory support diminishes work-family clashes, in this way expanding both family and career success fulfilment (Karatape et al., 2008).

Conduct of supervisors can be fundamentally related with the well-being of their workers. (Gilbreath et al., 2004). Researches show that supervisory support including emotional have impact on reducing the level of stress adding to the mental prosperity of worker (Cummins et al., 1990; Dubinsky et al., 1984). Informal supervisory support for work and family might be more vital to employee's general prosperity (Allen et al., 2001; Behson et al., 2005). Researchers exhibited that worker who received social and emotional support encounter a reduced amount of WFC (Anderson et al., 2002).

A supportive and helpful manager additionally has the capacity to facilitate work-family conflict so as to advance their generally speaking fulfilment with life, upgrade their organizational commitment, and lessen the intention of turnover (Hsu et al., 2010). Social help has significant impact on physical and emotional well-being and general life adjustment (House et al, 1981). Argyle et al., 1983, said social acknowledgment from boss, for example, compliments and support, can facilitate employees work family conflict. Past researches have additionally demonstrated that support from supervisor helps people diminish work-family conflict (Frye et al., 2004). Research indicated that a supervisor can enhance a worker's satisfaction and work execution by getting to be plainly associated with the employees' work-

family clashes (Carlson et al., 1999). Herriot et al., 1997, studied managers are normally critical people in organizations who are liable for keeping up the mental bond of workers. Past investigations have exhibited that supervisory help expands work fulfilment and diminishes work-family conflict (Hsu et al., 2011).

Above literature allows author to deduce the hypothesis:

H3: *Supervisory emotional support moderates the negative relationship of WFC and Employee well-being.*

Theoretical Framework

On the basis of available literature and its support, the following theoretical framework is designed which indicates relationship among all variables. It shows that WFC possess negative effect on employee's wellbeing. However, it shows that if supervisor's emotional support is available to employee, it enhances employees' well-being. This positive relationship between supervisor's emotional supports to employees' well-being, moderates the negative relationship between work-family conflict and employees' well-being.

3 Research design

The study is qualitative because data was collected through self-administered questionnaire. As the collected data is gathered from the respondents' at one time so data is cross sectional study. The target population was all employees of service providing industry situated in Skardu city, Pakistan such as schools, colleges, university, banks etc. because all types of employees faces work family conflict. The size of the sample was 150 employees. Both the genders i.e. male and female were targeted in this process of sampling. Through convenience sampling technique sample was done. After completing questionnaires, we coded and entered these responses into SPSS-17.0 (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) for further analysis.

3.1 Data Collection

Self-administered questionnaire was used to collect data. Age, gender and tenure in organization were included in demographic portion. Five item scale developed by Netemeyer et al., 1996, was used to determine WFC. Supervisory emotional support was measured with a four item scale developed by (Yoon et al., 1999). Employee's wellbeing was measured with the help of twelve item General Health questionnaire developed and validated by Goldberg et al., 1979.

3.2 Reliability Analysis of WFC, Supervisory Emotional Support and Employees' well-being

Cronbach Alpha for the entire variable is stated below in table along with no. of item for each variable. Cronbach's alpha larger than 7 is considered satisfactory (Nunnally et al., 1978). The item total statistics for reliability were:

Table 1: Reliability statistics

	Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
Work Family Conflict	.867	5
Supervisory Emotional Support	.714	4
Employees' Well Being	.825	12

Control Variables

Respondents' age, gender, and organization tenure are controlled variables for the study.

4 Results and Discussion

Descriptive statistics of three variables are shown in **Table 2**. For n=150, standard deviations minimum, maximum and mean values of each variable are presented in the table 2 below.

Mean value of work family conflict is 3.49 with standard deviation of 0.77 on a 5-point Likert scale, which shows the average score of responses of the respondents. The mean value of supervisory emotional support is 3.24 with a standard deviation of 0.83. For employees' well-being mean value is 1.91 with a standard deviation of 0.529.

The result shows that average response of respondents is 3.49 ± 0.77 or $3.49 - 0.77$ i.e. average response of respondents is around 3 (agree) in self-administered questionnaire. Furthermore, mean value of SES is 3.28 and standard deviation is 0.83. The result shows that average response of respondents is 3.28 ± 0.83 or $3.28 - 0.83$ i.e. the respondents chose the option slightly agree that SES has impact but not significant. Moreover, mean value of EWB is 1.08 and standard deviation is 0.52, predicting that the respondent's well-being is negatively affected more than usual because of WFC.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics table

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. deviation
WFC mean	1.40	5	3.49	0.77
SES mean	1	4	3.24	0.83
EWB mean	1.08	3	1.9111	.52984

Valid No. 150

4.1 Correlation Analysis

In order to find the relation between described independent and dependent variables correlation matrix was used. This matrix indicates that work family conflict is negatively correlated with dependent variable employees' well-being (-.674***, $p < .01$), which means as work family conflict increases employees well beings decreases by 67% and correlation is statistically significant. Supervisory emotional support is positively related with employees well-being (.368**) indicating as supervisory emotional support increases, employees well-being also increases and it's also statistically significant. Work family conflict is negatively correlated with supervisory emotional support (-.124) which means as supervisory emotional support increases work family conflict decreases by 12%.

Table 3. Correlation Analyses for Work family Conflict, Employees' Well-being and Supervisory Emotional Support

	WFC Mean	SES Mean	EWB Mean
WFC mean	1	-.124	-.674**
SES mean	-.124	1	.368**
EWB mean	-.674**	.368**	1

*** $p < 0.001$, $n = 150$. WFC= Work family Conflict, SES= Supervisory Emotional Support, EWB= Employees Well being

4.2 Regression Analysis

Three-step hierarchical regression analysis was used to test hypotheses 1 to 3. In the first step of analysis, the demographic variables (age, gender, tenure) were put in the regression model. In next step Work family conflict and Supervisory Emotional Support were entered into the model and in last step interaction term was entered to test moderator. Results are shown in **Table 4**.

Table 4. Hierarchical Regressions on EWB

Predictors	B	R ²	Significant
Step1			
Controls		0.075	
Step2			
WFC	-.775***	.604	0.00
SES	.196		0.52
Step3			
WFC*SES	.556***	.724	0.00

After running three step hierarchical regression it was found as control variables acted as insignificant predictors of variance in employees' well-being and explained only 7% effect on employees' well-being.

As Hypothesis 1 stated, WFC had a negative direct effect on employees well-being ($\beta = -.775$, $p=0.00$) here $R^2 = .604$ which means 1% increase in work family conflict causes to effect well-being of employees by 60% here $p=0.00$ so hypothesis 1 accepted whereas supervisory emotional support was found to have a positive impact but found no significant effect on employees well-being ($\beta = .196$, $p = .052$) here $p = .052$ so rejecting hypothesis 2.

However, the interaction term was significant, indicating that in case of indulging in WFC the supervisory emotional support causes to decrease the influence of work family conflict on employees' well-being hence third hypothesis is accepted and we can say that emotional support from one's supervisor does moderate the relationship between WFC and employees well-being. ($\beta=.556^{***}$ $p=0.00$). Here $R^2 = .724$ which means 1%change in interaction term of work family conflict and supervisory emotional support causes to effect employees well-being by 72%. In case of individual indulging in work family conflict supervisory emotional support provided by supervisor causes to effect work family conflict positively. $p=0.00$ so third hypothesis is accepted.

4.3 Discussion

The present study examined the impact of work family conflict on employees' well-being by taking supervisory emotional support as moderator. The finding of this study was, there is significant and negative relationship between employee's well-being and work family conflict, as in previous study conducted by (Lizano et al. 2014; Dobрева et al., 2002).

First hypothesis of the study was work family conflict has negative relation with employees well-being and results of this study came consequently hence first hypothesis of the study is accepted. Similarly, Netemeyer et al., 1996; Frone et al, 1992, found in their study that work family conflict is reliably connected to negative outcomes to families, people and organizations. It is related with work disappointment, life disappointment, goal to turnover, general well-being, mental strain, psychiatric disorder thus it causes to effect well-being of

the employees. Work-family conflict is related with reduction in performance, satisfaction and brings down well-being (Frone et al, 1992). Noor et al., 2010, reached on the conclusion that Work-family conflict is one of the major causes which induces stress and ultimately affects the employees psychologically and physically. Second hypothesis for the study was that supervisory emotional support increases well-being. Although supervisory emotional support positively affect well-being but no significant relationship was over there between supervisory emotional support and employee's wellbeing so hypothesis 2 is rejected. The author crossed interviewed the respondents majority of them said that as the people of Skardu, Pakistan leads a simple life, the culture followed by them doesn't allow them to share their personal life with anyone. It doesn't allow to interfere in one's personal life, providing emotional support means supervisor shows personal concern and affection to the employees which is not considered as acceptable in the region of Skardu. They are not used to share their personal life with anyone else except their close relatives and friend. Third hypothesis indicated that supervisory emotional support moderates the relationship between employees well-being and work family conflict. The result of this study proved this hypothesis right as well thus third hypothesis is also accepted. As, Duseath et al., 1995, said that support provided by immediate boss to the employees is one of the most significant forms of support at workplace which causes to reduce job stress. Manager's family-supportive behaviours (role modelling behaviours, instrumental support, creative work family management and emotional support) can cause to decrease work-to-family conflict (Behson et al., 2005). Karatepe et al., 2008, found in their study that Supervisory support has likewise been found to diminish work-family clashes, in this way expanding both family and career success fulfilment.

5 Recommendations

Managers, HR professionals along with all types of managers should understand the importance of well-being of their employees and give direction for management to focus on providing supervisory emotional support to them so that the organization will be able to have more satisfied employees. Organizations should establish day care center for its female members so that they can work more effectively in offices as their children can be look after in day care center in more better way. Organizational leaders and administrators can help balancing work and family life by introducing human resource programs like telecommunicating, flexible working hours, compressed work weeks etc.

5.1 Practical Implications and Direction for Future Research

This study will helpful for the young researchers to come up with new dimensions for assessing employees' well-being. The present study only examines the role of work to family conflict on employees well-being future studies should also examine the impact of family to work conflict on employees well-being by taking any other FSSB tool as moderator. As the data was collected from the employees serving in service providing industries located in Skardu only so the results and findings cannot be implemented in a common way for whole Pakistan. Future researchers are encouraged to collect samples from different populations in order to remove generalizes issue.

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